

Identification of bacterial blight (BB) pathotype of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* in Batalagoda, Sri Lanka

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To identify which genes confer resistance to the BB pathotype found in Batalagoda, we compared it with identified pathotypes from Japan, the Philippines, and India. Differential rice varieties from Japan and IRRI and selected varieties with resistance genes were inoculated at maximum tillering during 1990 dry season and 1990-91 wet season.

We evaluated plant resistance 2 wk after inoculation using *Standard evaluation system for rice*. The standard resistant check was DV85; standard susceptible varieties were Bg 34-6 and Seerage samba.

Pathogenicity patterns of the bacterial isolate from Batalagoda differed from those of the five pathotypes from Japan and four from the Philippines (see table), but were similar to that of the Indian pathotype group Ia. Only *xa 4*, *xa 7*, and *xa 13* confer resistance to the

Reaction of differential rice varieties of Japan and IRRI and selected varieties with BB-resistance genes to various BB pathotype groups identified in several countries.

Differential variety	Resistance gene identified	Reaction ^a to												Isolate from Batalagoda		
		Japanese pathotypes ^b					Philippine (IRRI) pathotypes ^c				Indian pathotypes ^d					
		I	II	III	IV	V	I	II	III	IV	Ia	Ib	II			
Kinmaze ^e	None	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S						
Kogyoku ^e	<i>Xa 1</i> <i>xa 12</i>	R	S	S	S	R	S	S	S	S						S
Tetep ^e	<i>Xa 1</i> <i>Xa 2</i>	R	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	S						S
Wasaikoku ^e	<i>Xa 3</i>	R	R	R	S	S	R	R	R	R						S
Java 14 ^e	<i>Xa 1</i> <i>Xa 3</i>	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	R			S
IR8 ^f	<i>xa 12</i> <i>Xa 11</i>	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR20 ^f	<i>Xa 1</i> <i>Xa 4</i>	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	S	S	R	S	S			MR
IR1545-339 ^f	<i>xa 12</i> <i>xa 5</i>	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S						S
DV85 ^f	<i>xa 5</i> <i>Xa 7</i>	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R		R
Cas 209 ^f	<i>Xa 10</i>	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	S				S	S	R	S
Campo-selek	<i>Xa 3</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	S	S				S
Chugoku 45	<i>Xa 3</i>	R	R	R	S	S	R	R	R	R						S
IR22	<i>Xa 4</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-						MR
Malagkit sungsong	<i>Xa-6</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-						S
Khao Loy Nhay	<i>xa 9</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-						S
Bj-1	<i>xa 13</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	R	R	S		R	
TN1	<i>Xa 14</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	S	S	S		S	
Bg 34-6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	S
Seerage samba	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	S

^aS = susceptible, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant. ^bRecorded in 1980. ^cRecorded in 1980. ^eJapanese differential variety. ^fIRRI differential variety.

pathotype found in Batalagoda, supporting an earlier observation that South

Asian pathotypes are more virulent than those of Japan and the Philippines. □

Evaluation of chitinase production as a criterion for selecting bacterial antagonists for biological control of rice sheath blight (ShB)

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Chitinase may have a role in hydrolyzing the chitin in cell walls of *Rhizoctonia solani* and thus reduce the pathogen's aggressiveness. We studied whether strong chitinase production in a strain correlates with its ability to inhibit *R. solani* growth in agar plates and suppress ShB in rice plants.

Evaluation of bacterial strains for suppression of ShB in IR50. Madras, India, 1990-91.

Bacterial strain	Chitinase production ^a	ShB suppression (%)		Bacterial strain	Chitinase production ^a	ShB suppression (%)	
		Greenhouse	Field			Greenhouse	Field
NF83	1	50.4	0.0	F80	4	68.5	4.9
NF100	1	68.0	8.8	F88	0	33.5	13.3
NF101	1	0.0	1.9	F92	4	34.6	3.7
NF104	3	3.8	14.0	F100	0	45.4	12.0
NF110	1	52.6	9.2	F1	100	76.9	15.4
NF118	5	12.8	2.9	F111	0	67.7	19.2
NF124	3	51.4	6.5	F114	0	48.8	5.9
NF164	5	33.9	12.2	F115	0	47.4	15.5
NF181	4	49.0	4.0	F125	0	62.1	21.3
NF188	0	58.5	18.7	F126	0	9.7	18.2
NF227	5	52.6	19.7	F141	2	0.0	16.7
NF243	0	47.5	9.6	F142	0	28.8	20.7
NF336	0	56.2	5.1	F145	2	70.4	18.4
NF340	2	25.4	0.0	F147	0	28.8	20.7
NF353	2	3.4	0.0	F156	4	28.8	21.5
NF354	1	55.4	5.0	F158	0	45.4	15.0
F6	2	72.1	34.3	F159	0	0.0	20.4
F11	0	12.7	19.2	F160	0	49.3	16.2
F12	0	47.8	32.8	F161	0	43.4	3.5
F75	0	43.6	6.6	Check		0.0	0.0
F76	0	38.9	18.9				

^a0 = negative, 1-3 = weakly positive, 4-5 = strongly positive.

We screened more than 1,000 bacterial strains for chitinase production by using 4-methylumbelliferyl N-acetyl B-D-glucosaminide (4-Muf. Glc NAc) to detect chitinase activity. Chitinase is a product of the degradation of chitin by chitinase. Chitinase and chitinase are produced concomitantly.

Bacteria were incubated at 37 °C for 10 min in 4-Muf. Glc NAc (Sigma) buffered substrate solution. Cells were then covered with one drop of a saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and exposed to UV light at 366 nm. Chitinase produc-

ers showed intense blue fluorescence and were scored on a 1-5 scale (see table).

Of the total bacterial strains, 43% were negative for chitinase production, 33.6% were weak producers, and 23.4% were strong producers. The 40 bacterial strains that were shortlisted (on the basis of pathogen inhibition) for greenhouse and seedbed evaluations showed no correlation between chitinase production and inhibition of *R. solani* in in vitro tests. Chitinase production and ShB suppression did not correlate in the greenhouse and field (seedbed) either (see table).

The fluorescent strains (F6, F12, F125, F14.5) that suppressed ShB most in greenhouse and seedbed tests of IR50 rice produced no or very little chitinase. Strain F6 suppressed ShB the best but had weak chitinase activity.

It appears that the chitinase production test is not the sole indicator in selecting promising bacterial strains for biological control. Promising strains that do not produce chitinase may have other disease suppression actions. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Influence of lunar phase on yellow stem borer (YSB) attraction to light trap

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We studied the effect of lunar phases on YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) moth light trap catches. Two modified Robinson light traps, one with a 125-watt mercury vapor lamp (MRL-T 125 W) and the other with a 200-watt incandescent

bulb (MRL-T 200 W), were used to attract moths for 12 lunar months from Apr 1988 to Mar 1989.

We categorized moth catches into four

lunar phases: full moon, last quarter, new moon, and first quarter.

The number of moths caught in traps during different lunar phases did not vary significantly (see table). □

Influence of lunar phase on light trap catch of YSB moths.

Trap	YSB moths ^a (no.)			
	Full moon	Last quarter	New moon	First quarter
MRL-T 125 W	29.66 (4.221)	55.75 (5.697)	58.08 (6.257)	28.58 (4.682)
MRL-T 200 W	42.92 (5.614)	97.85 (8.024)	143.25 (9.700)	54.75 (6.511)

^aMean of 12 lunar months. Figures in parentheses are transformed values.

Effect of foliar insecticide sprays on rice leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée and rice yield

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A field trial with 10 treatments and four replications was laid out in a randomized complete block design in a farmer's field in central Thailand in 1989. Rice variety RD7 was transplanted into 5- × 6-m plots. Using a knapsack sprayer, we applied insecticides diluted with 500 liters of water/ha at 20, 35, and 50 d after transplanting (DT).

Effects of foliar insecticide sprays on LF control and yield in the field, Chachoengsao, Thailand, 1989 dry season.

Insecticide	Rate (g ai/ha)	LF-damaged leaves (no./20 hills) at 50 DT ^a	Yield (t/ha)
BPMC	300	102.00 bc	3.9
BPMC + a cypermethrin	410	34.25 a	3.6
BPMC + a cypermethrin	520	12.25 a	3.7
Buprofezin	50	100.75 bc	3.7
Buprofezin	100	118.00 bc	3.1
Buprofezin + MIPC	250	131.75 bc	3.6
Buprofezin + fenvalerate	75	13.75 a	3.7
BPMC + fenvalerate	525	7.25 a	3.8
Monocrotophos	300	92.75 b	3.9
Control		140.25 c	3.7

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. DT = days after transplanting.

Average number of LF-damaged leaves at 50 DT significantly differed among treatments (see table). Plots sprayed with BPMC + fenvalerate, buprofezin + fenvalerate, and BPMC +

a cypermethrin had less leaf damage.

Yields were not significantly different among plots, indicating that high LF damage may not decrease yield. □